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Annotatsiya: Bir jinsli bo'lmagan sterjenda issiqlik almashish jarayonini boshqarish masalasi ko'rilgan. Boshqaruv masalasi parabolik tipdagi bir jinsli bo'lmagan tenglamaga qo'yilgan. Masalani yechishda differensial operatorlarning spektral nazaryasining Furye usulidan foydalanib yechimi topilgan. Masalaning matematik modeli tuzilgan. Uning yechimining mavjudligi va yagonaligi isbotlangan. Boshqaruv funksiyasi topilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Parabolik tipdagi tenglama, Furye usuli, Laplas tenglamasi xos funksiya, xos son, boshlang'ich shart, chegaraviy shart,

Hozirgi vaqtda fan texnikaning rivojlanishi ko'plab jarayonlarni nafaqat o'rganish, balki boshqarish imkoniyatlarini ham bermoqda. Juda ko'plab fizik jarayonlarni tadqiq qilish differensial tenglama va matematik fizika masalarini o'rganishga keladi. Bunga sodda misol qilib ma'lum hududning haroratini aniq temperaturada saqlash masalasini keltirish mumkin.

ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI

Ayni paytda xususiy hosilali differensial tenglamalar bilan tavsiflanuvchi jarayonlarni boshqarish masalalari jadal o'rganilmoqda.. Bu yo'nalishda birinchi bo'lib fransiyalik olim J.L.Lions shug'ullangan. Keyinchalik V.Barbu, A. Rascanu, G. Tessitore, H.O.Fattorini. A.V.Fursikov qator ilmiy natijalar olingan. O'zimizdan shu sohada ilmiy tadqiqot ishlarini olib borayotgan akademik Sh.Alimov "On A Control Problem Associated With The Heat Transfer Process"(2010) va S. Albeverio, SH. Alimov, "On a time-optimal control problem associated with the heat exchange process"(2008) maqolalarida issiqlik almashish jarayonini optimal boshqarish masalasi ko'rilgan. Z.K.Fayozova "Граничное управление процессом теплообмена"(2013) maqolasida bir jinsli issiqlik tarqalish tenglamasi uchun boshqaruv funksiya topilgan. Y. E. Fayziyev, N. Xalilova "О задача управления процессом теплопроводности" (2010) maqolada bir jinsli bo'lmagan issiqlik tarqalish tenglamasi uchun boshqaruv funksiya topilgan. Ilmiy natijalar [1], [2],[3],[4] ishlarda berilgan.

TADQIQOT METODOLOGIYASI.

Maqolada bir jinsli bo'lmagan issiqlik tarqalish tenglamasi uchun boshlang'ich chegaraviy, hamda sterjenning vaqt mobaynida o'rtacha temperaturasini berilgan holatda ushlab turuvchi shartlar qo'yilgan. Bir jinsli bo'lmagan sterjenning bir uchida boshqaruv funksiya qo'yilgan bo'lib, funksiyani topish uchun differensial operatorlarning spektral nazaryasi usullaridan ya'ni Furye usulidan keng foydalanilgan, hamda Laplas almashtirish, Millen almashtirish bajarilgan.

TAHLILLAR VA NATIJALAR

Quyidagi sohada $D = \{(x, t) : 0 < t < T, 0 < x < l\}$ issiqlik tarqalish tenglamasi va chegaraviy va boshlang'ich shartlarni qaraylik.

$$u_t(x, t) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(k(x) \frac{\partial u(x, t)}{\partial x} \right) + f(x, t), \quad 0 < x < l; t > 0; \quad (1)$$

$$u(0, t) = \mu(t), \quad u(l, t) = 0; \quad (2)$$

$$u(x, 0) = \varphi(x). \quad (3)$$

bu yerda $k(x)$ sterjen materiali tarkibini xarakterlovchi funksiya, $f(x, t)$ esa sterjen ichida issiqlik chiqaruvchi yoki yutuvchi manba funksiyasi, $\mu(t)$ sterjen chetida issiqlikni boshqarish funksiyasi, $\varphi(x)$ -sterjenning boshlang'ich holati.

$$(2) \text{ va } (3) \text{ shartdan } u(0, 0) = \varphi(0) = \mu(0), \quad u(l, 0) = \varphi(l) = 0, \text{ teng} \quad (4)$$

Boshqaruv funksiyasi $\mu(t)$ ni chegaralangan deb faraz qilamiz:

$$|\mu(t)| \leq M. \quad (5)$$

Sterjenning o'rtacha temperaturasi

$$\frac{1}{l} \int_0^l u(x, t) dx = b(t) \quad (6)$$

kabi belgilaymiz. (6)shart sterjenning vaqt mobaynida o'rtacha temperaturasini berilgan holatda ushlab turishni ko'rsatadi.

Masalaning qo'yilishi. $b(t)$ funksiya berilgan bo'lsin. U holda shunday $\mu(t)$ boshqaruv funksiyasini topish kerakki (1)-(3) masala yagona yechimga ega bo'lsin va bu yechim (6) shartni qanoatlantirsin.

Ushbu masalani yechishda berilgan funksiyalar uchun quyidagi talablarni qo'yamiz.

$$k(x) \in C^1[0; l], \quad k(x) > k_0 > 0,$$

Teorema. Berilgan funksiyalarimiz quyidagi sinfga tegishli bo'lsin .

$$k(x) \in C^1[0; l], \quad k(x) > k_0 > 0, \quad \varphi \in C[0, l] \quad f(x, t) \in C[0; l] \times C(R_+) \text{ va}$$

$$\mu \in C^1[0, +\infty]. \text{ U holda (1)-(4) masalaning yechimi mavjud va yagona.}$$

Isbot. (1)-(3) masalani yechish uchun Furrye usulidan foydalanamiz. Natijada quyidagi xos qiymat masalasini qaraymiz:

$$-\frac{d}{dx} \left(k(x) \frac{d\varphi_n(x)}{dx} \right) = \lambda_n^2 \varphi_n(x), \quad \varphi_n(0) = \varphi_n(l) = 0 \quad (7)$$

Differensial operatorlarning spektral nazaryasi kursidan ma'lumki (7) xos qiymat masalasi

yechimga ega va bu masalaning yechimlari bo'lgan $\{\varphi_n(x)\}$ xos funksiyalari sistemasi

$L_2[0; l]$ fazoda ortonormal bazis tashkil qiladi ya'ni:

$$\int_0^l \varphi_n(y)\varphi_m(y)dy = \delta_{nm} = \begin{cases} 1, & n = m, \\ 0, & n \neq m. \end{cases} \quad G(x, y; t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\lambda_n^2 t} \varphi_n(x)\varphi_n(y) \quad (8)$$

(1)-(3) masalaning umumiy yechimini Grin funksiyasi orqali ifodalaymiz

$$u(x, t) = \omega(x, t) + \int_0^t \int_0^l G(x, \xi; t - \tau) \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} \left\{ k(\xi) \frac{\partial \omega(\xi, \tau)}{\partial \xi} \right\} - \frac{\partial \omega(\xi, \tau)}{\partial \tau} \right] d\xi d\tau +$$

$$- \int_0^l G(x, \xi; t) \omega(\xi, 0) d\xi + \int_0^t \int_0^l G(x, \xi; t - \tau) f(\xi; \tau) d\xi d\tau + \int_0^l G(x, \xi; t) \varphi(\xi) d\xi \quad (9)$$

$$u(x, t) = k(0) \int_0^t \mu(\tau) \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} G(x, 0; t - \tau) d\tau +$$

Demak,

$$+ \int_0^t \int_0^l G(x, \xi; t - \tau) f(\xi; \tau) d\xi d\tau + \int_0^l G(x, \xi; t) \varphi(\xi) d\xi. \quad (10)$$

Oldimizga qo'yilgan masalani yechish uchun (10) ifodani (6) shartga qo'yamiz.

$$\int_0^t \mu(\tau) \left\{ \frac{1}{l} k(0) \int_0^l \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} G(x, 0; t - \tau) dx \right\} d\tau = b(t) -$$

$$- \int_0^t \left\{ \frac{1}{l} \int_0^l \int_0^l G(x, \xi; t - \tau) f(\xi; \tau) d\xi dx - \frac{1}{l} \int_0^l \int_0^l G(x, \xi; t) \varphi(\xi) d\xi dx \right\} d\tau.$$

Yuqoridagi tenglikni qulaylashtirish maqsadida ba'zi belgilashlarni kiritamiz.

$$K(t - \tau) = \frac{1}{l} k(0) \int_0^l \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} G(x, 0; t - \tau) dx = \frac{1}{l} \int_0^l \left\{ k(\xi) \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} G(x, \xi; t - \tau) \right\} \Big|_{\xi=0} dx$$

$$F(t) = - \int_0^t \left\{ \frac{1}{l} \int_0^l \int_0^l G(x, \xi; t - \tau) f(\xi; \tau) d\xi dx \right\} d\tau,$$

$$\Phi(t) = - \int_0^t \left\{ \frac{1}{l} \int_0^l \int_0^l G(x, \xi; t) \varphi(\xi) d\xi dx \right\} d\tau.$$

U holda biz quyidagi Volterra tenglomasiga kelamiz.

$$\int_0^t \mu(\tau) K(t - \tau) d\tau = b(t) + F(t) + \Phi(t) \quad (11)$$

(11) tenglamani yechish uchun Laplas almashtirish qo'llaymiz:

$$\int_0^{+\infty} e^{-pt} \left(\int_0^t \mu(\tau) K(t - \tau) d\tau \right) dt = \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-pt} \{ b(t) + F(t) + \Phi(t) \} dt,$$

bu yerda $p = a + is$ -kompleks son. U holda

$$\int_0^{+\infty} e^{-pt} \left(\int_0^t \mu(\tau) K(t-\tau) d\tau \right) dt = \int_0^{+\infty} \mu(\tau) e^{-p\tau} d\tau \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-p\lambda} K(\lambda) d\lambda = \widehat{\mu}(p) \widehat{K}(p)$$

$$\int_0^{+\infty} e^{-pt} \{b(t) + F(t) + \Phi(t)\} dt = \widehat{b}(p) + \widehat{F}(p) + \widehat{\Phi}(p).$$

$$\widehat{K}(p) = \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-pt} K(t) dt = \frac{1}{l} k(0) \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \varphi'_n(0) \int_0^l \varphi_n(x) dx \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-pt - \lambda_n^2 t} dt$$

$$\widehat{F}(p) = - \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-pt} \int_0^t \left\{ \frac{1}{l} \int_0^l G(x, \xi; t-\tau) f(\xi; \tau) d\xi dx \right\} d\tau dt$$

$$\widehat{\Phi}(p) = - \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-pt} \int_0^t \left\{ \frac{1}{l} \int_0^l G(x, \xi; t) \varphi(\xi) d\xi dx \right\} dt d\tau.$$

$$\widehat{\mu}(p) = \frac{\widehat{b}(p) + \widehat{F}(p) + \widehat{\Phi}(p)}{\widehat{K}(p)}.$$

Demak,

(12)

(12) tenglikda Mellin almashtirish bajarib $\mu(t)$ funksiyani topamiz.

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(t) &= \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{a-i\infty}^{a+i\infty} \frac{\widehat{b}(p) + \widehat{F}(p) + \widehat{\Phi}(p)}{\widehat{K}(p)} e^{pt} dp = \\ &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\widehat{b}(a+is) + \widehat{F}(a+is) + \widehat{\Phi}(a+is)}{\widehat{K}(a+is)} e^{(a+is)t} ds. \end{aligned}$$

Teorema isbotlandi.

Teorema. shunday $M > 0$ topilsinki, quyidagi shartlarni

$$\|b\|_{W_2^2(R_+)}^2 \leq M$$

va $b(0) = b'(0) = 0$ qanoatlantiradi.

Isbot. $\mu(t)$ funksiyani quyidan baholaymiz.

$$|\mu(t)| \leq \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{|\widehat{b}(i\xi) + \widehat{F}(i\xi) + \widehat{\Phi}(i\xi)|}{|\widehat{K}(i\xi)|} d\xi \leq \frac{1}{2\pi C_0} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |B(i\xi)| \sqrt{1 + \xi^2} d\xi.$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |B(i\xi)| \sqrt{1 + \xi^2} d\xi \leq C_1 \|b\|_{W_2^2(R_+)}^2.$$

shart o'rinli. Shuning uchun

$$|\mu(t)| \leq \frac{C_1}{2\pi C_0} \|b\|_{W_2^2(R_+)}^2 \leq \frac{C_1}{2\pi C_0} M = 1$$

$$M = \frac{2\pi C_0}{C_1} \text{ teng.}$$

Bu yerdan

Teorema isbotlandi.

XULOSALAR

Ko'rilgan masalada sterjen bir jinsli bo'lmagan va sterjen ichida issiqlik chiqaruvchi yoki yutuvchi manb'a joylashgan. Bu holda sterjenning o'rtacha haroratini aniqlash uchun uning

bir chetida boshqaruv funksiyasi qo'yildi va topildi. Boshqaruv funksiya $k(x)$, $f(x, t)$ funksiyalarga ham bog'liq ekan va ular quyidagi shartga ega bo'ldi...

$$k(x) \in C^1[0; l], k(x) > k_0 > 0, \varphi \in C[0, l], f(x, t) \in C[0; l] \times C(\mathbb{R}_+)$$

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